

Agroforestry carbon-farming: recommendations for Monitoring, Reporting and Verification

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Presentations

Introduction (5 minutes)

- [What is agroforestry in the CRCF?](#) (Gerry Lawson EURAF)

How to quantify agroforestry MRV (20 minutes)

- [Evaluating soil and biomass to determine climate effects of agroforestry](#) (Rico Hübner, DeFAF, Christian Böhm, Georg Eysel-Zahl, Sonja Kay, Wolfram Kudlich, Ernst Kürsten, Christopher Morhart, Konstantin Schwarz, Janos Michael Wack, Michael Weitz, Wolfgang Zehlius-Eckert)
- [Modelling of agroforestry](#) (Waas Thissen, Louis Bolk Inst; Christian Dupraz, INRAE; Kristoffer Ronn Anderson RegenFarmer, Paul Pardon, ILVO)

Implementation and additionality issues (10 minutes)

- [Regulatory and financial tests, including insurance, liability, leakage](#) (Bart van Beuzekom, Scature, Hanny van Hout, Climate Cleanup)

Sustainability issues (20 minutes)

- [AGES - social ecological agroforest: opportunities beyond carbon](#) (Chiara Michelone, Antonio Di Giorgio DEAFAL)
- [Climate adaptation and the environment: insights from the European projects DIGITAF, AGROMIX, and UNDERTREES](#) (Alberto Mantino, Univ Pisa)

Summary

Recommendations are given to support the role of agroforestry in future voluntary carbon-farming schemes. CAP eco-schemes, investment measures and agri-environment-climate measures during the first 5 years of agroforestry plantations can kick-start their adoption into voluntary carbon farming schemes, and help close the growing gap between GHG emissions and sequestration in rural Europe. A simplified and measurable definition of agroforestry is given, together with recommendations for agroforestry models to be used with measure-model verification methods. It is suggested that Member States should register and map lines and groups of trees as “landscape features”, and this will give them a protected status and good guarantees of “permanence”. For DGCLIMA to create a geospatial register of carbon farming parcels it is recommended that all Member States make CAP monitoring geospatial information available through their open-access “INSPIRE” portals, and that the agricultural data should be spatially-resolved and merged with similar forestry data.

Recommendations

An initial version of these recommendations was discussed during the workshop, and published on [Zenodo](#). The text below has been revised by the workshop presenters. It is structured around the sections in the DGCLIMA initial proposals for MRV of the CRCF activity titled “Soil carbon on mineral soils and agroforestry” ([Nov 2024](#))

1. Definitions

Agroforestry should be defined in the CRCF as “**Cropland or permanent pasture parcels**, including boundaries, with more than [x%] tree-cover-density (TCD)², or with a management plan where tree cover will exceed this density. The threshold TCD shall be set by Member States. **Permanent crop parcels** can be classed as agroforestry if a secondary crop or grazing is noted in the IACS-LPIS system” **Notes:** a) Member states are recommended to choose either **5%** (FAO threshold for “other wooded land”) or **10%** (FAO threshold for “forest”)

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² The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service publishes 100m and 10m [tree-cover-density](#) (TCD) products, covering the whole of Europe. Data for 2018 is available and 2022 is expected soon. The Horizon Europe [DigitAF](#) project is calculating the %TCD of all GSAA-LPIS parcels in selected EU countries. This will help quantify the status of agroforestry across as much of the EU as possible, and can be repeated every 3 years as new data is provided by Copernicus.

for the TCD threshold; d) IACS-LPIS “forest parcels” will not count as CRCF agroforestry, although forest grazing is a valuable management practice to reduce the risk of wildfires; c) Member States already use tree cover thresholds between 10% and 30% in their national definitions of “forest” (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#)).

Landscape features are quoted in the DGCLIMA draft methodology for carbon farming as “high diversity landscape features”, and are listed in Annex IV of the *Nature Restoration Regulation* (NRR [2024/1991](#)) as indicators of agricultural biodiversity. Unfortunately, DGENV uses a different definition of landscape features to that used in the CAP. *CAP Implementing Regulation* (L/458/463) Article 3.1 defines **landscape features** as “hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, trees rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features”. The NRR includes these categories, but also adds “land lying fallow”. It uses the prefix “high diversity” without clarifying what this means! DGAGRI and DGENV, with the help of JRC and their recent *Classification of Farming Practices* ([2024](#)), should resolve the differences in definitions urgently. The authors recommend that the **DGAGRI definition is preferred**, since it has existed for much longer and because Member States already provide detailed dimensions and rules for landscape features in their CAP Strategic Plans (EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#)).

Forest is defined as in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation [2018/841](#), amended for ES, SL and FI by Regulation [2023/839](#). The national thresholds conform with the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accords ([2021](#)) and are used by all Member States for their annual Greenhouse Gas Inventory Reports to the UNFCCC. The single definition of forest contained in the draft Forest Monitoring Regulation ([Nov 2023](#)) is **not appropriate** for CRCF reporting, except in the 3 MS where it matches the national definition.

Agroforestation is a shorthand term for the creation of agroforestry systems. It is the parallel of afforestation, but the land remains defined as “agriculture” rather than “forest” in national cadastres and IACS systems.

2. General Comments

The Carbon Farming Delegated Act should include an indicative list of carbon farming practices, based on the *Carbon Farming Technical Guidance Handbook* ([2021](#)) and the JRC *Classification of Farming Practices* ([2024](#)).

A standardised baseline of zero for agroforestry trees younger than 6 years, suggested by DGCLIMA, is appropriate since the modest growth of young trees in widely-spaced tree rows will be balanced by the small emissions caused by initial ground preparation and planting. Even tree-plantations with fast growth, such as poplars in the Po valley or eucalyptus in Galicia will fix less than 5% of their total biomass during the first 5 years. This availability of CAP funding for the baseline soil measurements, tree-planting and initial maintenance will “kick-start” accounting and greatly incentivise landowners.

Another type of agroforestation is protected natural regeneration of degraded wood pastures (e.g. Dehesas, Montados and Streuobst). There may be as much as 20.3 Mha of wood pastures in Europe ([Pleininger et al 2015](#)) and most are heavily degraded. Their restoration would be enhanced by a combination of CAP funding and carbon-farming certification. “Restoration of wood pastures” as a type of agroforestry will require establishment of a “project baseline” rather than a “standardised baseline” because of the presence of both mature and juvenile trees.

The second carbon farming methodology recommended by DGCLIMA is “*Tree planting on degraded and abandoned land*”. EURAF recommend that this be called “*Afforestation of degraded and abandoned land*” to avoid confusion with agroforestry (which remains as “agriculture” in CAP statistics), and to align better with existing UNFCCC and VCM methodologies for “*afforestation, reforestation and restoration*” (ARR).

3. Eligible Activities

In the DGCLIMA first MRV draft ([Nov 2024](#)), the discussion of carbon-sequestration should be completed with the statement “*or which reduce emissions from soils*”. This is particularly relevant to agroforestry - since agricultural trees can both limit N₂O emissions from the soil by uptake of surplus NO_x in reducing conditions, and reduce volatilized ammonia (NH₃) through its absorption on tree foliage. These processes should, ideally, be included in biophysical agroforestry models.

The DGCLIMA draft states that “*all farm activities must be monitored in case of leakage to non-certified parcels*”. EURAF feels this may dissuade farmers from applying for certification and could complicate use of the DGCLIMA geospatial carbon certification registry.

4. Activity Period and Monitoring Period

The minimum **activity period**³ proposed by DG CLIMA of 10 years is acceptable.. This is the shortest period possible for an agroforestry rotation (e.g. for poplars in the Po Valley). Most rotations will be 20-50 years.

The minimum **monitoring period**⁴ for agroforestry should also be 10 years. Again, if trees are 5 years old when monitoring starts they will be 20 when monitoring stops. This is too old for some fast-growing agroforestry.

5. Total carbon removals and/or soil emission reductions

DGCLIMA should maintain a list of “approved” agroforestry models/tools for certification. The DigitAF project has a provisional list of list such tools in its page on Tools, Data and Projects

Agroforestry projects should make projections using at least 3 different “approved” models/tools to gain an estimate of “uncertainty”

6. Addressing Uncertainties in a Conservative manner

Measure-Remeasure techniques may be unreliable in agroforestry for below ground biomass and fine root turnover because of 3-dimensional spatial variability. A modelling approach is inevitable and some existing models were recommended in the Dublin workshop ([Thissen 2025](#))

Almost all crop-management methods suggested in the *Carbon Farming Technical Guidance Handbook* ([2021](#)) can be used in the crop-alleys of agroforestry systems. One exception is a 100% no till system, where a subsoiler of chisel plough will need to pass close to the tree-lines, at least every second year, to ensure that tree roots do not compete excessively with crops in the surface soil horizons.

Branch pruning increases fine root turnover in proportion to the loss of above ground living biomass and should be included in biophysical and statistical models of agroforestry.

Strong links are needed with research projects like DigitAF, Reforest, MARVIC and MRV4SOC. These can help develop allometric equations to convert tree height and diameter to above and below-ground biomass. Allometry derived from forest stands will be inaccurate because trees have different form factors and less below ground biomass. Existing databases like BAAD, GlobAllomeTree, and FigShare, Mendeley therefore need to be extended for open-grown trees.

7. Additionality - Financial Test

In the CAP 2014-2022, across the EU, only around 5k hectares of agroforestry were planted from a target of 89k

In the CAP 2023-2028 only 9 countries have agroforestry measures, often with very low support rates and implementation in only a few regions (IT, ES, DE). The measures shown in Table 1 include financial support for afforestation. The agroforestry component is a small part of the total, but breakdowns are not available on the DGAGRI portal. No Member State provides a complete package of support: i.e. including each of Article 31, Article 73 and Article 70.

³ A period during which the activity generates a net carbon removal benefit or a net soil emission reduction benefit, and which is determined in the applicable certification methodology.

⁴ A period during which the soil emission reduction or storage of carbon is monitored by an operator or a group of operators and which covers at least the activity period, and which is determined in the applicable certification methodology

Table 1 - CAP Eco Scheme (Article 31), Investment (Article 73) and Agroenvironnement (Article 70) support for agroforestry in the CAP 2023-2028.

MS	Article	Code	O.16 (total)	R.17 (total)	Measure
BE-FL	Art 70	3.7	€281,384		Management of agroforestry systems (boslandbouwsystemen)
CZ	Art 70	26.7	€1,357,200		Caring for an established agroforestry system
CZ	Art 73-74	42.73		€3,917,700	Establishment of an agroforestry system
DE	Art 31	DZ-0403 –			Maintaining agroforestry management on arable land and permanent grassland
EL	Art 31	P1-31.05 –		€66,564,568	Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems, rich in landscape elements
ES	Art 70	6502.2	€27,069,248		Maintenance of Forests and Agroforests
ES	Art 73-74	6881.1		€68,809,809	Non productive investments in afforestation and agroforestry systems
IT	Art 70	SRA28	€66,080,718	€66,080,718	Support for maintenance of forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems
IT	Art 73/74	SRD05		€47,387,981	Forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems on agricultural land
PL	Art 70	I.8.8			Afforestation and afforestation premiums and agroforestry schemes
PL	Art 73-74	I 10.13.		€5,998,785	Establishment of agroforestry systems
PT	Art 70	C.1.1.3			Agroforestry Mosaic (Attributed to O.14 and R.14, R31, R.33)
PT	Art 70	D.2.2			Management of the montado (agroforestry) by Results
PT	Art 73-74	C.3.2.2		€3,360,000	Setting up agroforestry systems
PT	Art 73-74	F.2.2		€300,000	Investment in the creation and regeneration of agroforestry systems
SK	Art 70	70.01	€2,932,150	€2,932,150	Protection and maintenance of trees within the established Agroforestry system
SK	Art 73-74	73.01		€2,932,150	Establishing an agroforestry system

For agroforestry-carbon-farming to succeed it is vital that 4 linked interventions are offered in all Member States

- A. **Initial soil sampling and planning** - year 0, CAP Article 31 Eco Scheme
- B. **Planting and protection of trees** - year 1, CAP Article 73 investment Measure - possibly also Article 74 for irrigation.
- C. **Early years maintenance support** - years 2-5, CAP Article 70 - Agri Environment Climate annual payment
- D. **Adoption into a registered agroforestry carbon farming scheme** - from year 6 onwards, following satisfactory tree and soil monitoring.

8. Guarantee of Permanence - Landscape Features

Most carbon farming schemes approach the need for "permanence" of carbon removals by requiring operators to guarantee that carbon sequestration practices will be maintained for a minimum period. For afforestation (ARR) certification this assumes a given rotation period. In most countries, afforestation projects involve permanent change in land use, and carbon certification operators are required to maintain the forested areas in perpetuity. At the end of a plantation rotation, operators are required to obtain a felling licence from the forest authorities, and must regenerate the felled area, or in exceptional circumstances they can establish a similar area of forest nearby. This degree of permanence also applies to trees, lines of trees and small groups of trees which are recognised and mapped as **GAEC8 landscape features** on agricultural land.

Thus, in the LPIS systems of Member States it is important to distinguish agroforestry-carbon-farming systems where lines of trees have been formally mapped as woody landscape features (using PMEF Result Indicator 17.4) from those where trees are not mapped in this way (e.g. parkland areas with scattered trees). This legal "guarantee of permanence" could be reflected in the carbon price offered in the same way as with carbon in afforestation and reforestation projects.

Some Member States don't implement or map "Landscape Features" (e.g. FI, SE, MT). Further discussions with these Member States will be appropriate if agroforestry-carbon-farming is to be encouraged across Europe

Those Member States which map landscape features in their IACS-GSAA-LPIS systems do so in different ways.. In the CAP 2007-2014 they were recorded in a separate Ecological Focus Area layer of the LPIS as polygons or polylines (ref to Wimś paper on layers). The EFA layer is (Van der Weldle, pers comm)is now being integrated in the main GSAA layer, but it is very unclear how much progress Member States are making with this.

Also unclear is the degree to which Member States make their GSAA and LPIS data available openly through their INSPIRE portals, although openness of this data has improved markedly in the past year (Table 2), and is being exploited in the Regenfarmer/DigitAF “[LPIS aggregator](#)”

Table 2 Geospatial Aid Application (GSAA) and Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) information available from Member States through the [INSPIRE](#) and [DG AGRI Geoportals](#). To be supplemented with searches on a country by country basis (more details [here](#)).

Country	DGAgri Geoportal		INSPIRE Geoportal		Total All Sources	
	GSAA	LPIS	GSAA	LPIS	GSAA/LPIS	Name
Austria	y	y	y	y	y	LPIS
Belgium-Flanders	y	y	y	y	y	LPIS
Belgium-Wallonia	y	n	y	y	y	SIGEC
Bulgaria	n	(y)	n	n	n	LPIS
Croatia	n	y	n	y	n	LOIS-CROLIS
Cyprus	y	y	n	n	y	LPIS
Czech Republic	(y)	(y)	y	y	y	LPIS
Denmark	n	n	(n)	y	y	Markblokke
Estonia	y	y	y	y	y	LPIS
Finland	y	y	y	n	y	FLPIS
France	n	n	n	n	y	LPIS
Germany (16)	7	9	(y)	(y)	9	9
Greece	n	n	n	n	n	OPEKEPE
Hungary	n	n	n	n	n	MePAR
Ireland	n	y	y	y	y	LPIS
Italy	n	n	n	n	1	SIPA
Latvia	y	n	y	y	y	LAD
Lithuania	(y)	(y)	n	y	y	LPIS
Luxembourg	n	y	y	y	y	FLIK
Malta	n	n	n	n	n	LPIS
Netherlands	y	y	n	y	y	LPIS
Poland	n	y	n	n	n	ARIMA-LPIS
Portugal	n	y	y	y	y	IFAP-Parcelaria
Romania	n	n	n	(n)	n	APIA-LPIS
Slovakia	y	y	y	y	y	LPIS
Slovenia	y	n	y	y	y	GERK/RABA
Spain	n	n	y	y	y	SIGPAC
Sweden	n	y	y	n	y	jordbruksblock

The [DigitAF](#) project is seeking to superimpose Copernicus % Tree Cover Density onto LPIS data for a range of countries in the EU ([Milestone 6 Report](#)). This will give an indication of the current extent of agroforestry and allow future planting to focus on the [detailed areas](#) and [NUTS3 provinces](#) which have the highest proportion of “tree deserts”.

The IACS-GSAA-LPIS data only contains “active farmers” whose minimum payments range between €100 and €500 and/or have minimum holding areas ranging from 0.3 ha to 4 ha (depending on the Member States). The DG CLIMA Register of Carbon Farming, which is [due to be developed by 2028](#), will need to include codes for parcels owned by smaller farmers and also forest parcels. Some form of link to cadastral codes is also possible.

Governments could underwrite the risk of accidental loss of carbon by fire or other damage to trees. This insurance option requires further investigation. An advantage of agroforestry compared to conventional afforestation is that fires are much less likely, and less damaging if they do occur ([Wolpert et al 2022](#)).

9. Calculation of Standardised Baselines

CAP GSAA and LPIS systems show the location of agroforestry parcels and woody landscape features: the latter usually in a separate Ecological Focus Area (EFA) layer. Member states vary significantly in the access they provide to this data and in the classifications used. Greater harmonisation and open data access is needed for the DGCLIMA geospatial parcel register of carbon farming parcels which is promised by 2028. Sentinel 2 data gives Tree Crown Density data at 10m resolution. This is useful for broad summaries, but agroforestry carbon farming needs access to <50cm resolution Orthophotos, and probably also lidar data.

Standardised baselines in the CRCF are intended to calculate the average carbon capture in an area given knowledge of local climate, soil type and cropping patterns⁵. They could be used to measure the sequestration and emission reduction impact of a farmer against peers in similar areas. Ideally, the comparisons should be carried out using **pedoclimatic zones** (e.g. [Toth 2016](#)) rather than political areas like NUTS2 or NUTS3, but these it is not certain that these classifications exist in sufficient details. The authors initially thought that standardised baselines could be based on GSAA-LPIS Municipality (NUTS4) data, but the areas of these seem too small and variable to be of practical use in most Member States (Table 3). **Another option would be to fix a 10x10 km “bounding box” around each farm applying for carbon certification and calculate a “standardised baseline” using the average land use and soil information derived from GSAA-LPIS for the whole 10 kha box.**

Table 3 Numbers and dimensions of NUTS4 (LAU) districts in EU Member States ([EEA 2025](#))

MS	NUTS3	NUTS4	AV (ha)	Min (ha)	Max (ha)
AT	36	2,093	4,008	11	46,689
BE	44	581	5,282	116	21,534
BG	28	265	41,886	4440	136,570
CY	1	615	1,503	28	15,383
CZ	14	6,258	1,260	42	49,621
DE	400	10,979	326	3	8,911
DK	11	99	43,386	0	147,350
EE	5	79	55,018	381	271,852
EL	53	6,142	2,149	23	57,516
ES	59	8,132	6,207	883	175,023
FI	19	309	126,707	600	1,733,367
FR	101	34,946	?	?	?
HR	21	556	10,173	605	96,745
HU	20	3,155	2,949	149	52,511
IE	8	166	42,330	462	186,586
IT	108	7,900	4,366	221	128,673
LT	10	60	108,811	3943	221,585
LU	1	100	2,586	529	11,336
LV	5	43	150,218	1750	359,106
MT	2	68	?	?	?
NL	40	342	9,838	701	52,270
PL	73	2,477	12,674	332	68,300
PT	26	3,092	2,983	20	88,835
RO	42	3,181	7,494	141	81,462
SE	21	290	140,439	868	1,916,165
SI	12	212	9,562	693	55,561
SK	8	2,927	1,676	36	35,978

10. Suggested Agroforestry Management Plan

EURAF suggested in a submission to DG FISMA (EURAF [Policy Briefing #28](#)) that Climate Delegated Act of the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation should reinsert the initially proposed section on sustainable agriculture. The Delegated Act should contain sustainable management criteria for agroforestry, alongside the existing sections on forestry and paludiculture. The structure suggested for an agroforestry carbon-farming management plan was as follows.

⁵ wording in the CRCF Regulation is “*The certification methodologies should establish standardised baselines which should be highly representative of the standard performance of comparable practices and processes in similar social, economic, environmental, regulatory and technological circumstances and take into account the geographical context, including local pedoclimatic and regulatory conditions*”

- A. Location of the parcels and boundaries using codes from the national IACS/LPIS system (or equivalent)
- B. Location of neighbouring forest and agricultural blocks, showing habitat linkages between wooded areas and the role of ACF parcels in fire-management plans for adjacent forests.
- C. Baseline estimates of carbon-stocks in each certified parcel including soils and above-ground biomass
- D. Management goals, design, species and predicted carbon sequestration of areas covered by trees
- E. Management goals and predicted carbon sequestration of the intercropped or grazed alleys;
- F. Environmental context of the farm(s), including main existing and intended tree species
- G. Details of access, environmental constraints, registered landscape-features and legal restrictions on land-use change;
- H. Details of engagement with neighbours and local stakeholders, in accordance best practice nationally;
- I. Assessment of agroforestry related risks, including fires, pests and diseases outbreaks and plans to mitigate these
- J. Assessment of impact on food production of the farm(s) included in the plan;
- K. Evaluation of “co-benefits” for biodiversity
- L. Evaluation of “do no significant harm” (DNSH) criteria for other areas of “sustainability”